

FIELD TESTING OF A STANDING COLUMN WELL LOCATED IN THE NICOLET FORMATION

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Abstract

A dynamic thermal response test is conducted on an experimental standing column well located in the Nicolet Formation to evaluate the impact of bleed on its thermal performance. Results suggest that a bleed rate of 7.5 L/min increases the apparent thermal conductivity by 2.5 times compared with a no-bleed scenario.

1. Introduction

Standing column wells (SCW) are efficient ground heat exchangers that rely on the recirculation of groundwater in a deep and uncased borehole. “Bleeding” the well (discharging a small amount of groundwater) has been identified as a key feature of SCWs performance. The capacity to bleed the well can however be limited in areas with a low bedrock hydraulic conductivity. The objective of this short paper is to evaluate the influence of a realistic bleed operation on the thermal performance of an experimental SCW located in the Nicolet Formation.

2. Methods and techniques

A thermal response test is conducted on an experimental system made of a 215-m-deep SCW and a 150-m-deep injection well. The latter allows reinjection of the bleed water. Groundwater is recirculated in the SCW at a rate of 75 L/min for 18 days. Two 4-day heating phases are carried out using a 24-kW water heater. Bleed rate is 0 L/min during phase 1, and 7.5 L/min (10% of the total pumping rate) during phase 2. Note that bleed rate cannot be further increased without overflowing the injection well due to the low bedrock hydraulic conductivity that is 5.7e-7 m/s (Beaudry *et al.* 2019). Temperatures at the SCW’s inlet and outlet are monitored and the apparent thermal conductivity for both phases is computed using the infinite line source theory (Mogensen 1983).

3. Results

The apparent thermal conductivity measured for the first heating phase of the test involving no bleed is 2.42 W/mK, whereas it is 6.11 W/mK for the second heating phase involving a 7.5 L/min bleed. The mean temperature evolution during the test is shown in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1 Inlet - outlet mean temperature during the test.

4. Discussion

Visual inspection of the results shows that discharging 7.5 L/min tempers the temperature variation inside the SCW. This enhanced thermal efficiency translates as an apparent thermal conductivity value that is 2.5 times higher than in the no-bleed scenario. These results are mostly attributable to the stimulation of advective heat transfer when bleed acts as a net pumping rate, which creates a drawdown and promotes renewal of the well’s water content.

5. Conclusions

It was demonstrated in this study that discharging 7.5 L/min (10% ratio) enhances heat transfer around an experimental SCW and increases the apparent thermal conductivity by about 2.5 times. These findings suggest that bleed remains a key feature of SCW operation even if the system is located in a hydrogeological unit characterized by a low bedrock hydraulic conductivity such as the Nicolet Formation.

References

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